

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: BUSHELL****FIRST NAME: NADINE****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: ONE (1)****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

1. Essay Writing (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 10-14)
2. Punctuations (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 15-23)
3. American versus British English (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 33-39)
5. Style Guide (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 40-42)
6. CMS Crib Sheet (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 43-57)
7. Latin Abbreviations and Expressions (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 58-64)

ACA-401 PERIOD 1 REVIEW

1) INTRODUCTION

The material for the course ACA-401 period one gives the student initial guidance on how to conduct advanced academic writing. The main areas covered in this course pack were, essay writing, using punctuation appropriately, American versus British style English, plagiarism, understanding what a style guide and the need is for one, the Chicago style and Latin abbreviations and expressions.

Authors Professor Laurent Cleenewerck and Dr. Kabiru Gulma in the preface to the module state: “This fourth edition of the period one course pack provides international academic and professional paper writing basics. The first study material introduces students to academic writing at Euclid University” (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021).

This course was a very useful introduction to students to help them improve their academic writing skills as they undertake their doctoral programs.

2) REACTION TO THE STUDY MATERIAL

a) Essay Writing

The chapter on essay writing gave me the basics of academic essay writing. Academic essay writing refers to “nonfictional writing produced as part of academic work. Examples of academic writing include research findings or report on empirical fieldwork which may not or may be published in journals, books, newspapers, or other periodicals (or remain as manuscripts, theses, or dissertations); monograph; conference paper; book or literature review; explication; technical report; translation; students’ presentations; as well as undergraduate versions on the above” (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 7).

I got a clear understanding of the process that should be undertaken to ensure that the final product is sound. The essay writing process commences with determining the question to be asked, followed by research, then the organisation of my ideas in relation to the topic. Once these steps are completed then writing the essay can commence using the appropriate references. Of course, it is critical to review the essay before handing it in. This detailed process was not unfamiliar to me, based on my professional experience. Through my various job positions, I have written a number of policy and research papers and strategy documents. These are done on a very regular basis.

I was slightly amused though with the guidelines for handing in the essay, as this referred to physical submission. I thought that in the year 2022 and after the COVID-19 pandemic, this is unlikely to be a popular mode of submitting assignments.

The rules of thumb identified on pages twelve to fourteen of Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, listed hereunder, I think are quite critical to writing a successful academic paper. These are:

- state the main thesis of your paper at (or near) the beginning
- stay focused
- do not lead with (or conclude with, or otherwise include) sweeping generalities
- write clearly
- do not make the writing boring and clumsy
- support assertions
- take the views you are discussing seriously
- do not plagiarize

b) Punctuations

The second topic of punctuation, I found very fascinating; this was because it was really something I never gave any thought to. Over the years that I have been writing various papers, I assumed that my use of punctuation was appropriate. I particularly found

the following statement very instructive “Use as little punctuation as necessary while retaining the meaning of the sentence” (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 16). I will definitely be paying attention to this aspect of my writing. I referred to the chapter for parts of this response paper. This chapter will be kept close throughout this Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) process.

c) American versus British English

The use of American versus British English has always been something that I would have encountered particularly in my professional life. As a student many years ago, throughout primary, secondary, and university education, both in Trinidad and Tobago and in the United Kingdom, it was made clear that as students we were to follow British English. This would have been mainly in reference to spelling. Professionally, however, this has not been clear-cut. I have worked in International and Regional Organizations, where I have interacted with many different stakeholders, from varying cultures and countries. There was never any stated requirement as to which style was preferable. It depended largely on the preference of the organization or the reader. The discussion on British versus American English though is much larger than spelling. Consideration must also be given to the following in academic writing:

- different or additional meanings
- same concept, different terms, or expressions
- politically correct terms and/or references

This list is not exhaustive as there are other facets to be considered, but I thought these were very critical for academic writing, and I will be now paying attention to this aspect of my writing.

d) Plagiarism

This section had the most significant impact on me, especially the discussion of knowing what plagiarism is, and how to avoid it. According to Cleenewerck & Gulma (2021, 34), plagiarism is defined as “when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information”. While this may appear straightforward, based on the descriptions and explanations given in the chapter, there may be instances where persons may not realize that the way they have written or referred to something can be classed as plagiarism. The points under the Paraphrases subsection brought this home to me. I never thought that writing in my own words the thoughts and ideas of an author would have been considered plagiarism. The fact is that paraphrases must meet the following criteria as outlined in Cleenewerck & Gulma (2021, 36) indicates to me that I need to be very careful in referring to and paraphrasing other persons’ written work when writing my dissertation:

“A. Must be YOUR words. The language you use cannot resemble the words of the author. So, this means you cannot just change a couple of words and rearrange the sentence structure

B. The writing style you use to express the author’s ideas must be different from the style the author used

C. The information that you are providing must be an accurate representation of what the author originally wrote

D. Finally, after doing all and indicating where the source of the above, you must still CITE the work information came from”

e) Style Guide

This was a completely new concept for me, and this will be something that will require significant effort on my part as I progress through this PhD program. I have also never heard of the Chicago Rules (Turabian). I never thought of myself as having an approach as a writer, or considering my preferences in relation to sentence length, active versus passive voice preferences or manuscript layout. I usually structure my sentences and paragraphs based on what I think makes the point most clearly, and often I try not to be longwinded. I do understand the need however for the need for a style guide, where you have multiple authors for various types of publications. This is well presented through this statement: “Style guides are generally associated with certain types of writing like technical writing, commercial or business writing, journalism, and web copywriting. In each of these cases, there is a need to ensure that the writing style is consistent. So, guidelines are usually published to allow more than one author to contribute while ensuring that the finished piece does not necessarily carry the personal style of the writer but that of the publication, company, or website associated with the writing. For publications or companies with many contributing authors, a style guide is essential if the finished publication is to be coherent and consistent” (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, 41).

However, because there was no reference to academic writing I wondered about the importance of a specific style to this group of writers. Admittedly, I have not wrapped my mind entirely around this component.

f) CMS Crib Sheet

“Chicago Style is the style of formatting books and research papers documented in the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS), 2003, and Kate Turabian’s Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, 1996 (both published by the University of Chicago Press)” (Cleenewerck & Gulma, 2021, 44).

The various elements of this style including but not limited to abbreviations, capitalization, compound words, italics, quotation marks, writing numbers and page formats, footnotes, and end notes are important to the professional appearance of your papers. This level of detail will also be very new for me. Even though I completed my

Master of Science program albeit twenty years ago, this level of attention to Chicago style is very unfamiliar.

g) Latin Abbreviations and Expressions

I have had some understanding that Latin contributed many words to the English Language. This chapter, particularly the table which spanned pages fifty-nine to sixty-four, Cleenewerck & Gulma 2021, gave examples of many Latin words and their English meanings, making me much more aware of the extent of the contribution. There were many words that are commonly used, that I did not know had Latin origin. Some examples include *circa* which means about or approximately, *confer* which means compare, and *pro tempore* which means for the time or temporarily.

3) CONCLUSION

For me, this module raised my awareness of the various elements of writing that I need to consider when doing my academic papers. Admittedly, this will require some getting used to, as now I do not write based on any particular style or structure, but rather based on what sounds good to me. This will definitely be a process of learning for me, and I expect that this Response Paper will be the first step in this journey.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 202. *ACA-401/ACA-401DCoursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

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